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Need Structure as Predictors of Opting Traditional and Non-traditional Entrepreneurship

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar**

With the purpose to examine the role of need structure dimensions (need for achievement, level of aspiration, sense of security and risk taking) in vocational preference amongst traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs and to examine the relationship amongst need structure dimensions, this empirical study was conducted on traditional (N = 40) and non-traditional (N = 40) male entrepreneurs belonging to urban Patna, Bihar. It was hypothesized that : There will be significant difference between traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs in terms of (i) need for achievement (ii) level of aspiration (iii) non-risk taking and (iv) sense of security traits respectively (v) There will be significant relationship among the need structure dimensions. The respondents were administered the Need for Achievement Scale by Mukherjee, Singh's Level of Aspiration Scale, Sense of Security / Insecurity Scale by Shanti Singh and Choubey's Risk-taking Scale respectively to measure the need for achievement, level of aspiration, sense of security and risk-taking as need structure dimensions respectively. Besides these, the respondents were administered the PDS to seek the necessary information about them. The obtained data were analysed using chi-square and Pearsonian 'r'. The results upheld the hypotheses. It was found that non-traditional entrepreneurs excelled over traditional entrepreneurs in terms of having higher level of each of need structure dimension under reference as compared to their counterparts. There were found a significant co-efficient of correlation amongst each need structure dimension (motivational components) under study. It was concluded that - (i) high and powerful need structure dimensions lead to the preference of non-traditional entrepreneurship whereas low and weak need structure dimensions lead to the preference of traditional entrepreneurship, (ii) The need structure dimensions possess a significant relationship with one another.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship refers to a process of action an entrepreneur undertakes to establish his/her enterprise. It is a creative and innovative response to the environment. It is a cycle of actions to fulfil the interests of the entrepreneurs. It is a composite skill of imagination, risk taking tendency, having use of production, capital, labour and land. The new concept of entrepreneur is as the person who detects and evaluates a new situation in his environment and directs the making of such adjustments in the economic systems as he deems necessary. Traditional entrepreneurship is one in which a person opts the vocation or occupation or business as per their family traditional for one's livelyhood, non-traditional entrepreneurship is one in which any one opts the occupational or business for livelyhood directed from one's family traditions. Another component of the present study is need for achievement which refers to the tendency to strive for success or attainment of the desired goal. Peter Straton and Nicky Hayes (1991) defined it as, "the motivation to accomplish valued goals and to avoid failure. Next component of the present study is level of aspiration which refers to as an individuals goal or expectation in regard to his godness of his own future setting behaviour

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which occurs within the range of difficulty of the individuals. It reflects an individuals ambitions in dynamic situations. Chaplin (1975) defined it as a self imposed standard against which a person judges his own performance. Level of aspiration varies with the pattern of success or failure. Risk taking is, further, an important component of the present study which refers to a hypothetical personality dimension reflecting the degree to which an individual willingly undertakes actions that involve a significant degree or risks. Security/Insecurity is also an important component of the present study. Chaplin defined security as the state of feeling of being safe and non-apprehensive about the future satisfaction of one's need. Insecurity is the feeling of being unable to cope, feeling unsafe, threatened, and anxious. Reber et al (2009) defined security as a sense of confidence, safety, freedom from fear or anxiety, particularly with respect to fulfilling one's present need. Insecurity is lack of assurance, uncertainty, unapproachableness.

Various studies have been conducted in India but without the direct inclusion of variable under reference. The present study will serve the exploratory and confirmatory objectives of the study. The above reasons are indicative of the fact that the undertaking of the present study is justified.

Objectives

The study intends to make comparison of need structure dimensions namely : (i) need for achievement, (ii) level of aspiration, (iii) non-risk taking and (iv) sense of security between traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs. Further, it was intended to examine the relationship among need structure dimensions.

Hypotheses

There will be significant difference between traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs in terms of (i) need for achievement (ii) level of aspiration (iii) non-risk taking and (iv) sense of security traits respectively (v) There will be significant relationship among the need structure dimensions.

Method of Study

Sample Used

The sample comprised of 40 traditional and 40 non-traditional male entrepreneurs selected from various organizations of Patna town based on purposive sampling.

Research Tools Used

- Achievement Motive Scale by Mukherjee was used for measuring need for achievement of the respondents.
- Level of Aspiration Scale by Singh was administered for measuring aspiration level of the respondents.
- Non-Risk Taking Scale by Chaubey was used for measuring the risk-taking trait of the entrepreneurs.
- Security/Insecurity Scale by Shanti Singh was used for assessing the sense of Security/Insecurity of the respondents.
- A PDS was employed on the respondents to get the necessary informations about the respondents.

Procedure of Data Collection

The Scales were employed on the respondents in different phases and informations were gathered. The data were obtained as per the directions of the manuals of tests concerned. The data were analysed using t-test given below :

Results

Table - 01

Comparison of Traditional and Non-traditional male entrepreneurs in respect of need for achievement motivation.

Variable	Male Entrepreneurst-value				P (df = 78)
	Traditional (N= 40)		Non-traditional (N= 40)		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Need for Achievement	15.91	6.84	27.24	6.79	7.45
	<.01				

It is clear from result table-01 that traditional and non-traditional male entrepreneurs differ significantly in terms of need for achievement dimension. Non-traditional entrepreneurs manifested higher mean (27.24) than traditional entrepreneurs (15.91). The t-value was found significant ($t = 7.45$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. one is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the ground of higher degree of self-confidence and development and growth of self-related personal traits more on the part of non-traditional entrepreneurs than traditional entrepreneurs leading to the results.

Table - 02

Comparison between traditional and non-traditional male entrepreneurs in context of level of aspiration motivation.

Variable	Male Entrepreneurs				t-value (df = 78)	P
	Traditional (N = 40)		Non-traditional (N = 40)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Level of Aspiration	15.17	6.28	25.29	6.47	7.08	
	<.01					

It is clear from the result table that non-traditional male entrepreneurs excelled (Mean = 25.29) over traditional male entrepreneurs (Mean = 15.17). In terms of level of aspiration. The t-value was found significant ($t = 7.08$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (2) is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the characteristics of need structure dimensions including level of aspiration.

Table - 03

Comparison between traditional and non-traditional male entrepreneurs in terms of non-risk taking trait of need structure dimension.

Variable	Male Entrepreneurs				t-value (df = 78)	P
	Traditional (N = 40)		Non-traditional (N = 40)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Non-Risk taking	42.97	6.55	31.38	6.26	8.10	
	<.01					

It is clear from the findings that traditional entrepreneurs excelled (Mean = 42.97) over non-traditional (Mean = 31.38) male entrepreneurs in terms of non-risk taking trait significantly ($t = 8.10$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$). It means that non-traditional male entrepreneurs prefer in taking risk. However, traditional male entrepreneurs are not found high risk takers. Thus, hypothesis no. 03 is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the ground of risk taking. Those entrepreneurs who are not willing to take risks are inclined to opt traditional entrepreneurship as such their vocational choice involve minimum risk. On the other hand

entrepreneurs who are willing to take more risks to achieve success are inclined to opt non-traditional entrepreneurship.

Table - 04

Comparison between traditional and non-traditional entrepreneurs in terms of security/insecurity dimension of need structural motivations.

Variable	Male Entrepreneurs				t-value (df = 78)	P
	Traditional (N= 40)		Non-traditional (N= 40)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Security/Insecurity	38.16	6.45	49.66	6.92	7.67	
	<.01					

The findings of table-04 clearly revealed that non-traditional entrepreneurs excelled (Mean = 49.66) over traditional (Mean = 38.16) male entrepreneurs in terms of sense of security significantly ($t = 7.67$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (04) was retained. The findings can be interpreted in terms of the characteristics of security / insecurity. Interpretation can be done on the fact that entrepreneurs feeling secured while willing to opt traditional entrepreneurship. On the other hand entrepreneurs belonging to socio-economic advantages conditions feel more secured while opting non-traditional entrepreneurship as their vocation for the sake of the more profits in future.

Table-05

Pearsonian 'r' showing relationship among need structure dimensions.

Variables	N	r	df	p
Need for Achievement Vs Level of Aspiration	80	0.415	78	<.01
Need for Achievement Vs Risk Taking	80	0.407	78	<.01
Need for Achievement Vs Sense of Security	80	0.396	78	<.01
Level of Aspiration Vs Risk Taking	80	0.411	78	<.01
Level of Aspiration Vs Sense of Security	80	0.402	78	<.01
Risk Taking Vs Sense of Security	80	0.421	78	<.01

The results displayed by Table-2 clearly revealed that there is a significant positive correlation of NA Vs LA ($r = 0.415$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$); NA Vs RT ($r = 0.407$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$); NA Vs SS ($r = 0.415$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$), LA Vs SS ($r = 0.402$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$), and RT Vs SS ($r = 0.421$; $df = 78$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis is no. (2) is retained. The findings of table (2) is in agreement with findings of table (1). The interpretation remained the same.

Conclusions

- (1) The person opting non-traditional entrepreneurship excelled over their counterparts opting traditional entrepreneurship in terms of need structure dimensions (need for achievement, level of aspiration, risk taking and sense of security).
- (2) Need structure dimensions are significantly and positively correlated with each other.

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